

MIND AND PHYSICAL EXERCISE

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Introduction:

The mind is a set of cognitive faculties including consciousness, perception, thinking, judgement, language and memory. It is usually defined as the faculty of an entity's thought and consciousness. It holds the power of imagination recognition and appreciation and is responsible for processing feelings and emotions resulting in attitudes and actions. Physical exercise is the performance of some activity in order to develop or maintain physical fitness and overall health. Frequent and regular physical exercise is an important component in the prevention of some diseases such as heart diseases, cardiovascular diseases, Type 2 diabetes and obesity.

Physical Exercise and Mind:

Mind health is the balanced development of an individual's personality and emotional attitudes which enable him to live harmoniously with his fellow beings. Exercise has many benefits not only for your physical health but also your mind health .in your brain exercise stimulates chemicals that improve your mood and the parts of the brain responsible for memory and learning. Physical and mind activities are both important for protecting your thinking skill and warding off dementia. Regular exercise can increase the volume of brain regions important for memory and thinking. The different between a mind and physical exercise practitioner and a personal trainer is in the state of mind that the mind and physical practices. The state of mind is much more than simply concentration or mind attention but it is quite difficult to define. Physical exercise that is executed with a profound amount of directed focus and basically 5 characteristics of mind and physical exercise. Any mind and physical exercise will typically have one or even more of the below mentioned characteristics.

- ✓ Concentration on muscular movements
- ✓ Inner mental focus
- ✓ Synchronizing movements with breathing patterns
- ✓ The belief in life energy
- ✓ Attention to form and alignment.

Physical exercise can help to improve strong mind in number of ways:

- ✓ Physical exercise Reduce Stress: One of the most common mind benefits of exercise is stress relief. Working up a sweat can help manage physical and mind health. Exercise also increases concentrations of norepinephrine a chemical that can moderate the brain's response to stress, so get sweaty. Working out can reduce stress and boost the body's ability to deal with existing mind tension.
- ✓ Physical exercises boost happy chemicals: Experience release endorphins which create feelings of happiness and euphoria. Exercise can even alleviate symptoms among the clinically depressed. For this reason the people suffering from depression or anxiety. In some cases, exercise can be just as effective as antidepressant pills in treating depression.
- ✓ Physical exercise improve self confidence: On very basic level physical fitness can boost self esteem and improve positive self image. Regardless of weight, size, gender or age, exercise can quickly elevate a person's perception of his or her attractiveness that is self worth.
- ✓ Physical exercise help to enjoy great outdoor: Exercising in the great outdoors can increase self esteem even more. Find an outdoor workout that fits your style, whether its rock climbing, hiking, renting a canoe or just taking a jog in the park. All that vitamin D acquired from soaking up the sun can lessen the likelihood of experiencing depressive symptoms.
- ✓ Physical exercise prevent cognitive decline: It's unpleasant, but it's true as we get older our brains get a little hazy. As aging and degenerative diseases like Alzheimer's kill off brain cells, the noggin actually shrinks losing many important brain functions in the process. while exercise and a healthy diet can't cure alzheimer's,they can help shore up the brain against cognitive decline that begins after age 45 working out, especially between age25 and 45,boosts the chemicals in the brain that support and prevent degeneration of the hippocampus ,an important part of the brain for memory and learning.
- ✓ Physical exercise help alleviate anxiety: The warm and fuzzy chemicals that are released during and after exercise can help people with anxiety disorders calm down. Hopping on the track or treadmill for some moderate to high intensity aerobic exercise can reduce anxiety sensitivity. And we thought intervals were just a good way to burn calories
- ✓ Physical exercise boost brain power: Cardiovascular exercise can create new brain cells and improve overall brain performance. Tough workout increase the levels of brain derived protein in the body, believed to help with decision making, higher thinking and learning.
- ✓ Physical exercise sharpen memory: Regular physical exercise boosts memory and ability to learn new things. Getting sweaty increase production of cells in hippocampus responsible for memory and

learning, for this reason research has linked children's brain development with level of physical fitness. But exercise based brain power isn't just for kids. Even if it's not as fun as a game of red rover, working out can boost memory among grown ups, too. a study shows that running sprints improved vocabulary retention among healthy adults.

- ✓ Physical exercise help to control addiction: The brain release dopamine the reward chemical in response to any form of pleasure is that exercise, sex, drugs, alcohol or food. Unfortunately some people become addicted to dopamine and dependent on the substances that produce it, like drugs or alcohol. exercise can help in addiction recovery. Short exercise sessions can also effectively distract drug or alcohol addicts, making them de-prioritize cravings .exercise can help reboot the body clock helping people hit the hay at the right time.
- ✓ Physical exercise increase relaxation: A moderate workout can be the equivalent of a sleeping pill, even for people with insomnia. moving around five to six hours before bedtime raises the body's core temperature. When the body temperature back to normal a few hours later it signals the body that it's time to sleep.
- ✓ Physical exercise help get more done: Workers who take time for exercise on a regular basis are more productive and have more energy than their more sedentary peers. While busy schedule can make it tough to squeeze in a gym sessions in the middle of the day some experts believe that midday is the ideal time for a workout due to the body's circadian rhythms
- ✓ Physical exercise help to tap in to creativity: A heart pumping gym session can boost creativity for up to two hours afterwards. Supercharge post workout inspiration by exercise outdoors and interacting with nature. And need a burst of creative thinking hit the trails for a long walk or run to refresh the body and the brain at the same time
- ✓ Physical exercise helps to inspire others: Most people perform better on aerobic tests when paired up with a workout buddy. Working out can have positive effects far beyond the gym. Gaining self confidence getting out of a funk and even thinking smarter are some of the motivations to take time for exercise on regular basis

Mind Health Benefits of Exercise:

Exercises make feel good because it release chemical s like endorphins and serotonin that improve mind. It can also get out in the world, help to reduce any feelings of loneliness and isolation and put you in touch with other people. If you exercise regularly it can reduce stress and symptoms of mental health conditions like depression and anxiety and help with recovery from mind health issues. Exercise also helps improves your sleep which is important in many different ways.

Exercise and the Mind:

Exercise pumps blood to the brain, which should make you think more clearly. It increases the size of the hippocampus the part of the brain responsible for memory. It also increases the connections between the nerve cells in the brain. This improves your memory and helps protect your brain against injury and diseases.

How Much Exercise do you Need?

Adults do at least 30 minutes of moderate to intensive physical activity on most or all days of the week. You can make up to 30minutes over the day by combining shorter 10-15 minutes sessions. Practicing mindfulness while doing exercise also reduce your stress and improves your mind health. Combine your health routine with a healthy diet to boost your motivation and energy for exercise

References:

1. Journal of public mental health
2. International journal of mental health systems.
3. Peluso, M.A., &Guerra de Andrade, L.H. (2005).physical activity and mental health: the association between exercise and mood. Clinics, 60(1), 61-70.
4. Physical activity and mental health promotion: the natural partnership. Journal of public mental health, vol.2issue:1,pp.4-12